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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

5. Environmental Sciences

ITER Project: Improving Thermal Efficiency of hoRizontal ground heat exchangers

“Since shallow geothermal energy resource is becoming increasingly important as renewable energy resource, due to its huge potential in providing thermal energy for residential and tertiary buildings and in contributing to reduce greenhouse gas emission, the number of installed geothermal systems is expected to continue to rise in the near future.

Moreover, in this timeframe the population living in urban areas is expected to increase. This worldwide trend will lead to a high concentrations of infrastructures in confined areas, whose impact on land use and shallow subsurface must be well evaluated.

Aim of ITER Project (Improving Thermal Efficiency of hoRizontal ground heat exchangers, No. 661396), is to improve the heat transfer efficiency and ensure the sustainability of very shallow geothermal collectors and special forms (e.g. heat baskets), interesting the first 2 m of depth from ground level.

Key challenges are

- i. to enhance the heat transfer of the ground surrounding the pipes creating thermally enhanced backfilling material (TEBM) suitable for horizontal systems;
- ii. to assess the performance and the environmental impacts of new promising technological solutions as heat baskets with and without TEBM;
- iii. to monitor the results over time through direct measurements and numerical simulation, in order to understand the heat pollution effect in the surrounding environment.

Thermal laboratory measurements and in situ monitoring of existing and duly installed horizontal systems are provided by close cooperation between host institutions and non-academic partners.

A test site was realized in Eltersdorf, near Erlangen (Germany): 5 Helix probes (3m length) were installed at a depth of 0.6 m below the ground level and the

trenches were filled in with 5 different materials, ranging from natural material as fine sand (0-1 mm) till commercial products. Here are showed the preliminary results obtained during the first months of research activity.”

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